

Quantitative Structure– Activity Relationship on some 2-Hydroxy-1*H*-isoindole-diones as Cytostatic Agents

ARUN K. SRIVASTAVA*, N. MISHRA, D. K. GUPTA and ARBAB A. KHAN

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002

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The structure-activity relationship of 2-hydroxy-1*H*-isoindole-diones, which are cytostatic agents, has been discussed. The growth inhibitory potency of these compounds are found to be dominantly controlled by electronic and steric factors. Significant correlation have been obtained between the growth inhibitory potency and topological index (T).

The series of sixteen derivatives of 2-hydroxy-1*H*-isoindole-dione-1,3-diones act as potential antitumor agents. It was found that the most important functional group in hydroxyurea for the inhibition of ribonucleotide reductase (RR) is known to be the =CNHOH. RR is known to be an important enzyme in DNA synthesis. This enzyme catalyses one of the rate-determining steps in the synthesis of DNA. Its activity is found to correlate positively with the proliferation of cells. This correlation was found to be particularly high in fast growing malignant cells¹. Three other types of enzyme namely thymidylate synthetase, thymidine kinase and DNA polymerase are also involved in the synthesis of DNA but they are not as much active as that of RR². Thus, the selective inhibition of RR has been used as a part of the overall strategy in the design of chemotherapeutic agents. Of all the well known ribonucleotide reductase inhibitors, only hydroxyurea is found suitable for clinical use. Some of known RR inhibitors guanazoles and thiosemicarbazones, showed significant *in vitro* inhibition against cell growth but their *in vivo* toxicities have prevented them from being used in clinical applications³. Due to small size and highly polar nature, hydroxyurea possess a very short half-life and consequently its clinical use is limited. In order to circumvent the inherent problem of hydroxyurea frequent dosing regimen is required.

In order to design new potentially active compounds the hydroxyurea molecule was modified by Lien *et al.*⁴ in such a manner that the optimum balance of lipophilicity and hydrophobicity is obtained while the functional group =CNHOH is maintained. The present series of 2-hydroxy-1*H*-isoindole-1,3-diones possess various types of alkane and arenesulphonate group that serve as protective group for NOH moiety. The protective group enhances the efficiency of the compound by prolonging the half-life of the hydroxyurea molecule⁵.

In the present work the steric parameter T (topological index) and electronic parameter X_{eq} (equalised electronegativity) and δ_G (partial charge) have been used to assess the role of molecular size and electronic factor. T may be calculated as suggested by Pal *et al.*⁶, X_{eq} as suggested by Pauling⁷ and δ_G as defined by Sanderson⁸. In the present work Hammett substituent constant (σ) has also been used as one of the parameters whose value have been taken from the literature⁴. The purpose of the present QSAR studies is to provide a better drugs.

Results Discussion

The series of 2-hydroxy-1*H*-isoindole-dione-1,3-diones and their activity data are listed in Table 1. The physicochemical parameters used in the correlation are also listed in Table 1.

TABLE I—BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY AND PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PARAMETERS USED IN REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	T	X _{eq}	δ _G	σ	log 1/IC ₅₀			
							Observed	Calculated by		
								Eqn.(1)	Eqn.(4)	
1.	NH ₂	H	1.318 6	4.039 5	-1.657 9	-0.66	3.456	3.789	4.004	
2.	NH ₂	SO ₂ CH ₃	2.161 9	4.122 5	-3.021 1	-0.66	5.481	5.105	5.250	
3.	NH ₂	SO ₂ CH(CH ₃) ₂	2.546 4	4.520 4	-4.760 3	-0.66	6 000	5.705	5.818	
4.	NH ₂	SO ₂ C ₆ H ₅	2.365 9	3.975 9	-1.638 5	-0.66	5.509	5.423	5.552	
5.	(CH ₃) ₂ N	H	1.701 7	4.547 8	-3.880 0	-0.83	4.620	4.387	4.762	
6.	(CH ₃) ₂ N	SO ₂ CH ₃	2.606 8	4.520 4	-4.760 3	-0.83	7.036	6.846	6.927	
7.	(CH ₃) ₂ N	SO ₂ CH(CH ₃) ₂	2.991 6	4.835 6	-6.139 1	-0.83	6.721	6.400	6.579	
8.	(CH ₃) ₂ N	SO ₂ C ₆ H ₅	2.979 8	4.297 6	-2.992 7	-0.83	6.538	6.381	6.561	
9.	(CH ₃) ₂ N	SO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	2.987 8	4 437 8	-4.399 7	-0.83	6.638	6.394	6.573	
10.	(CH ₃) ₂ N	SO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂	55.792 0	3.085 0	4.102 3	-2.932 9	-0.83	6.721	6 545	6.717
11.	C ₆ H ₅ NH	SO ₂ CH ₃	44.974 8	2.689 6	4.520 4	-4.760 3	-0.61	6.468	5.928	6.000
12.	C ₂ H ₅ NH	SO ₂ CH(CH ₃) ₂	50.109 1	3.074 3	4.835 6	-6.139 1	-0.61	6 149	6.529	6.568
13.	C ₂ H ₅ NH	SO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	59.642 7	3.070 6	4.437 8	-4.399 7	-0.61	6.167	6.523	6.563
14.	NO ₂	SO ₂ CH ₃	32.910 0	2.279 0	3.794 7	-1.457 4	-0.78	4.745	5.288	4.556
15.	NO ₂	SO ₂ CH(CH ₃) ₂	40.349 9	2.663 8	4.169 9	-3.228 7	0.78	4.658	5.888	5.125
16.	H	SO ₂ CH ₃	25.067 7	2.168 1	4.012 5	-1.540 4	0.00	5.530	5.115	4.862

Before studying the correlation between the activity log (1/IC₅₀) (where IC₅₀ is the nanomolar concentration of drug required to reduce the growth of drug required to reduce the growth of L 1210 cell by 50%)⁴, and the three calculated parameters T, X_{eq}, δ_G and σ we have checked for any autocorrelation and found that only X_{eq} and δ_G exhibit autocorrelation.

The log (1/IC₅₀) is found to be significantly correlated with T (topological index) as shown by

$$\log (1/IC_{50}) = 1.560 T + 1.732 \quad (1)$$

$$n = 16, r = 0.87, F = 40.77, s = 0.49$$

where n is the number of data points, r the correlation coefficient, s the standard deviation, F the F ratio between the variance of calculated

and observed activities, and with (±) sign within the parenthesis are the 99% confidence intervals. The electronic parameters X_{eq} and δ_G exhibit poor correlation with activity (r = 0.44) and (r = 0.57) respectively. When either of the electronic parameters X_{eq} or δ_G are taken along with steric parameter T, no change in the value of r is observed as mentioned in equations (2) and (3) respectively,

$$\log (1/IC_{50}) = 1.449 T + 0.429 X_{eq} + 0.164 \quad (2)$$

$$n = 16, r = 0.87, F = 20.56, s = 0.49$$

$$\log (1/IC_{50}) = 1.444 T - 0.069 \delta_G + 1.781 \quad (3)$$

$$n = 16, r = 0.87, F = 18, 72, s = 0.52$$

However, when steric parameter T (topochemical index) along with σ taken into consideration with activity, correlation level was found to be quite significant,

$$\log(1/IC_{50}) = 1.447 T - 0.602 \delta + 1.657 \quad (4)$$

$$n = 16, r = 0.93, F = 41.05, s = 0.37$$

and F -value is found to be significant at 99% level $|F_{(3,12)}| = (.01) = 5.951$.

It can be predicted from the above equations that an increase in substituent size as represented by topochemical index (T) will cause an increase in the activity, whereas the negative sign of coefficient of σ in equation will make it clear that any increase in Hammett substituent σ will result in an increase in activity.

A close study of Table 1 makes it very clear that the smallest molecules **1** and **5** are also least active. It is interesting to note that compound **5** which contains the important N,N -dimethylamino group shows very poor activity whereas the larger molecules **6–10** containing dimethyl amine group exhibit much greater activity.

The QSAR studies performed⁴ earlier between the activity the hydrophobic parameter R_m and electronic parameter σ showed a large correlation.

The present study shows that in addition to the hydrophobic and electronic factors, the steric factor as represented by T (topochemical index) also contributes significantly towards determining the activity of this series of drugs.

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